

A Study of Catechol Disulphonic Acid and Chromotropic Acid Derivatives of Aluminium

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Complex formation reactions of aluminium with chelating agents, disodium salt of catechol disulphonic acid (Tiron) and chromotropic acid, have been studied by potentiometric and conductometric methods.

In the acidic solution of both the systems, the formation of mono derivatives only is indicated even in presence of a large excess of chelating agents. The equilibrium constant, K , of the reaction:

and the logarithms of the formation constants (K_1) of the complex anion (AlA^-) in Tiron and chromotropic acid systems have been found to be 3.55×10^{-4} , 16.81 and 1.82×10^{-4} , and 17.22 respectively. The logarithms of the formation constants ($\log K_n$) for 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 complexes in the Tiron system have also been determined by alternative methods to be 17.02 ± 0.23 , 16.40 ± 0.21 , and 14.30 ± 0.07 and for 1:1 and 1:2 complexes (in chromotropic acid system), 17.53 ± 0.13 and 16.78 ± 0.08 respectively.

The disodium salt of catechol disulphonic and chromotropic acids, having two acidic hydrogen atoms [$(K_{a1} = 2.188 \times 10^{-9}$ and $K_{a2} = 2.512 \times 10^{-13}$] and [$K_{a1} = 4.365 \times 10^{-6}$ and $K_{a2} = 2.512 \times 10^{-16}$] are strong chelating agents and form derivatives with a number of metallic ions³⁻⁶. Some studies⁷⁻⁹ have already been made on the nature and stability of complex formation of aluminium with Tiron and chromotropic acid. No attempt appears to have been, however, made to evaluate the formation constants from the functions $\bar{n}$ and $[\text{A}^{4-}]$. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to make a detailed study on the systems by potentiometric and conductometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of E. Merck aluminium nitrate $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared by direct weighing and the strengths were checked gravimetrically as oxinate. The disodium salts of catechol disulphonic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Na}_2\text{O}_8\text{S}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and chromotropic acid [$(\text{OH})_2 \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}(\text{SO}_3\text{Na})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] were recrystallised E. Merck products. The solutions of these chelating

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The potentiometric titration of aluminium nitrate in presence of equimolar concentration of Tiron (curve 1, Fig. 2) shows a sharp inflection at $m = 2$ (m = mole of alkali added per mole of the metal ion), indicating the formation of aluminium monocatechol disulphonate derivative (A) according to the reaction:

The titration curve has a well-defined but sloping inflection between 3 and 4 equivalents of alkali, indicating that the complexes might contain one to two hydroxyl ions attached to each metal ion. Although much more detailed work is essential to define the exact nature of these complexes, these may be represented by the following type of polynuclear structure, similar to those assumed by Intorre and Martell¹⁰ for the corresponding zirconium system.

Curve 2 (Fig. 2) for the potentiometric titration of aluminium nitrate in presence of 2 moles of Tiron shows inflections at $m = 2$ and 4, indicating formation of aluminium monocatechol disulphonate (A) and dicatechol disulphonate (B) derivatives, respectively.

Potentiometric titration of aluminium nitrate with NaOH in presence of 3 moles of Tiron (curve 3, Fig. 2) shows inflections at $m = 2, 4,$ and $6,$ indicating stepwise formation of mono-(A), di- (B), and tri-catechol disulphonate derivative of type (C), respectively.

Similar titration of aluminium nitrate in presence of 4 moles of Tiron (curve 4, Fig. 2) shows inflections at $m = 2$ and $4,$ indicating the formation of mono- (A) and di-catechol

disulphonate (B), respectively. Another inflection at $m = 7$, occurring at $\text{pH} \approx 9.8$, is probably due to presence of excess of Tiron in the system.

The reactions involving the formation the monochromotropate derivative along with the hydrolysed products and dichromotropate derivative can be represented by the following equations which are similar to those given in the Tiron system.

FIG. 3. Curves 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 represent potentiometric titrations of aluminium nitrate (0.005M, 20ml) with NaOH (0.1M) in presence of 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 ml of chromotropic acid (0.1M). (m = mole of base added per mole of aluminium ion).

However, in the present studies with chromotropic acid as chelating agent, no indication could be found for the 1:3 derivatives similar to those found with Tiron. The apparent reason for this appears to be steric hindrance which may be caused to the association of three chromotropic acid molecules round an aluminium ion.

Conductometric Studies

The conductometric titration of aluminium nitrate with NaOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 moles for Tiron (curves 0, 1, 2 and 3, Fig. 4) showed inflections in corroboration of those obtained in the potentiometric studies. When NaOH was replaced by the weak

base, NH_4OH (curves 0, 1, 2, and 3, Fig. 5), the presence of only the mono- and dicatechol disulphonate derivatives was indicated. In the case of ammonium hydroxide, the formation of 1:3 complexes, which are formed in more alkaline range (as shown by the potentiometric titration curves), is not indicated and the conductance of aluminium nitrate—Tiron mixtures becomes constant after 4 moles of ammonium hydroxide have been added in both the cases, i.e., when the molar ratio of Tiron: aluminium is 2 or 3.

FIG. 4. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent conductometric titrations of aluminium nitrate (20ml, $1 \times 10^{-3}M$) with $0.02M$ - NaOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3ml of $0.02M$ Tiron.

FIG. 5. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent conductometric titrations of 20 ml ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) aluminium nitrate with $0.1M$ - NH_4OH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of $0.1M$ Tiron.

The conductometric studies of aluminium—chromotropic acid system (Fig. 6,7) are in close agreement with the conclusions drawn from potentiometric titrations.

Equilibrium and Formation Constants

As the monocatechol disulphonate and monochromotropate derivatives alone appear to be formed in the acidic range, it has been possible to determine their formation constants which have been calculated by first determining the equilibrium constants. Out of the possible equilibria for the formation of 1:1 complex, the following equilibrium:

was found to provide constant pK values.

For the above determinations, the ionic strength was maintained constant by using a medium containing 0.1M potassium nitrate and low concentrations of ligand and metal ions.

The equilibrium constant, K , for the reaction (i) is given by

$$K = \frac{[AlA^-][H^+]^2}{[Al^{3+}][H_2A^{2-}]} \quad (ii)$$

FIG. 6. Curves 0, 1, 2 and 3 represent titrations of aluminium nitrate (0.001M, 20 ml) with 0.02M-NaOH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of 0.02M chromotropic acid.

FIG. 7. Curves 0, 1, 2, and 3 represent titrations of aluminium nitrate ($2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$, 20 ml) with 0.05M-NH₄OH in presence of 0, 1, 2, and 3 ml of 0.05M chromotropic acid.

The value of K has been calculated from the concentrations of $[AlA^-]$, $[H^+]$, $[Al^{3+}]$, and (H_2A^{2-}) present in the equilibrium mixture. Over the pH range studied, the concentrations of $[HA^{3-}]$, $[A^{4-}]$, and $[OH^-]$ were negligible compared to the other ionic species present in the equilibrium mixture. The values of pK in both the systems have been calculated at various points on curves 1, 2, and 3 (Fig. 8 and 9) from $m=0$ to $m=1.8$, where m represents mole of base added per mole of the aluminium ions. The values of pK , calculated from the data of curves 1, 2, and 3 (Fig. 8 and 9), are shown in Tables I and II.

After determining the equilibrium constants ' K ' of the reactions (i), the forma-

tion constant K_1 of the complex anion (AlA^-) was determined from the following equation:

$$K_1 = \frac{K}{K_{a_1} K_{a_2}} \quad (iii)$$

where K_{a_1} and K_{a_2} represent dissociation constants of chelating agents. By substituting the various values in equation (iii), the values of $\log K_1$ were obtained as 16.81 and 17.22 in Tiron and chromotropic acid systems, respectively.

TABLE I

Equilibrium constants for aluminium-monocatechol disulphonate derivative.

NaOH (ml) ..	0.2	0.6	1.0	1.4	1.8	2.0	2.4	2.8	3.2	3.6	4.0	4.4	
For Al: Tiron=1:1 (curve 1).													
pH ..	3.43	3.49	3.53	3.59	3.65	3.68	3.76	3.84	3.94	4.06	4.21	4.43	
pK ..	3.48	3.47	3.44	3.45	3.43	3.42	3.43	3.42	3.42	3.42	3.40	*(3.36)	
												Mean pK	3.44
For Al: Tiron = 1:2 (curve 2).													
pH ..	3.32	3.36	3.40	3.44	3.49	3.52	3.58	3.65	3.72	3.81	3.93	4.11	
pK ..	3.47	3.46	3.44	3.42	3.42	3.43	3.44	3.46	3.45	3.44	3.45	3.47	
												Mean pK	3.45
For Al: Tiron = 1:3 (curve 3).													
pH ..	3.27	3.31	3.35	3.39	3.43	3.46	3.52	3.58	3.65	3.74	3.87	4.04	
pK ..	3.53	3.49	3.47	3.46	3.43	3.45	3.47	3.46	3.44	3.43	3.48	*(3.37)	
												Mean pK	3.46

*Neglected.

TABLE II

Equilibrium constants for the aluminium-monochromotropate derivative.

NaOH (ml) ..	0.2	0.6	1.0	1.4	1.8	2.2	2.6	3.0	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.6	
For Al: chromotropic acid = 1:1 (curve 1).													
pH ..	3.29	3.34	3.40	3.46	3.53	3.61	3.70	3.80	3.91	4.05	4.25	4.57	
pK ..	3.80	3.75	3.73	3.71	3.71	3.72	3.73	3.74	3.73	3.73	3.75	3.76	
												Mean pK	3.74
For Al: chromotropic acid = 1:2 (curve 2).													
pH ..	3.17	3.22	3.27	3.32	3.37	3.43	3.49	3.56	3.64	3.74	3.87	4.09	
pK ..	3.77	3.76	3.76	3.75	3.73	3.74	3.73	3.73	3.72	3.72	3.71	3.72	
												Mean pK	3.74
For chromotropic acid = 1:3 (curve 3).													
pH ..	3.11	3.15	3.20	3.24	3.29	3.35	3.41	3.47	3.55	3.65	3.79	4.00	
pK ..	3.75	3.73	3.74	3.72	3.72	3.72	3.73	3.71	3.72	3.73	3.74	3.68	
												Mean pK	3.73

Computation of Formation Constants from the Functions $\bar{n}$ and $[A^{4-}]$

The formation constants K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 for the systems:

were calculated from the titrations of Tiron or chromotropic acid and nitric acid in absence and presence of aluminium ions (curves 1 and 2, Fig. 10 and 11); the ionic strength of the medium was kept approximately constant by using 0.10M potassium nitrate solution. The values of $\bar{n}$ (average number of ligands per metal ion) were plotted against the values of pH (Fig. 12 and 13).

FIG. 8. Potentiometric titrations of aluminium nitrate with 0.10M-NaOH in presence of Tiron at 0.01M ionic strength: Curve 1: $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ Tiron. Curve 2: $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ Tiron. Curve 3: $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $1.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ Tiron. Total volume of the initial reaction mixture = 50 ml.

FIG. 9. Potentiometric titrations of aluminium nitrate with NaOH in presence of chromotropic acid at 0.10M ionic strength. Curve 1: $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ chromotropic acid. Curve 2: $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ chromotropic acid. Curve 3: $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ aluminium nitrate and $3 \times 10^{-3}M$ chromotropic acid. Total volume of initial mixture = 50 ml.

In the case of aluminium—Tiron system, after having read^{11,12} the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5, corrections were calculated by using (i) spreading factor¹³

11. Bjerrum, 'Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution', P. Haas and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.

12. Calvin and Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.

and (ii) corrections term methods¹³. Then, the $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ values were computed by similar methods and the values of $\log K_2$ were again treated similarly with the corrected values of $\log K_1$, and the process was continued till the final values recorded in Table IIIA were obtained. For comparison, values were also calculated by the least square treatment¹³. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in aluminium- chromotropic acid system have also been calculated by the alternative methods and the final values are shown in Table IIIB.

FIG. 10
Curve 1: Potentiometric titration of 50ml [$5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Tiron + $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO_3] with $0.02 M$ NaOH.
Curve 2: Same as 1 + $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ aluminium nitrate.

FIG. 11
Curve 1: Potentiometric titration of [$5 \times 10^{-3} M$ chromotropic acid + $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO_3].
Curve 2: Same as 1 + $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ aluminium nitrate.

FIG. 12. Degree of formation of $\bar{n}$ as a function of $-\log(\text{ligand})$ for Al-catechol disulphonate chelate.

FIG. 13. Degree of formation of $\bar{n}$ as a function of $-\log(\text{ligand})$ for the Al-chromotrope complex.

TABLE III

Methods.	Log K_1 .	Log K_2 .	Log K_3 .
A. Al—Tiron system.			
(i) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values ¹¹⁻¹³	17.11	16.46	14.23
(ii) Spreading factor method ¹¹	16.99	16.57	14.25
(iii) Correction term method ¹³	16.79	16.58	14.34
(iv) Least square treatment ¹³	17.17	16.28	14.36
B. Al—chromotropic acid system.			
(i) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	17.56	16.73	
(ii) Correction term method	17.40	16.86	
(iii) Least square treatment	17.61	16.73	

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